

NEGATION AS A LOGICAL-GRAMMATICAL CATEGORY

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Abstract: Negation is one of the inherently existing undivided semantically connotational categories characteristic of the entire linguistic picture of the world, which cannot be defined through simpler semantic elements. Negation can be expressed by negative words, a negative prefix, a negative form of a verb, and may also not be expressed separately, that is, as a component of the meaning of a word or an entire sentence.

Key words: Negation, affirmative sentence, infinitive, gerundial and participial constructions, opposite, category, component.

In modern linguistics, the problem of “negation” occupies a significant place and, despite the large number of researchers, has not been sufficiently studied. “Negation” as a term denotes an element of meaning in a sentence, indicating that the connection established between the components of the sentence does not take place in reality or that the opposite affirmative sentence is perceived by the speaker as contrary to the truth. In most cases, a negative statement is used in situations where the corresponding affirmative sentence has been used previously. Negation is one of the inherently existing undivided semantically connotational categories characteristic of the entire linguistic picture of the world, which cannot be defined through simpler semantic elements. Negation can be expressed by negative words, a negative prefix, a negative form of a verb, and may also not be expressed separately, that is, as a component of the meaning of a word or an entire sentence. Since there is nothing negative in the objective world, therefore, negation can be considered as a tool to prohibit something or express reluctance or disagreement with something, as well as reject someone's opinion. The category of denial includes the history of many centuries. A large number of scientific discussions that are devoted to the study of denial do not subside, in various approaches, only the angle of view on the problem and the analysis component of the consideration change. Negation is one of the main concepts in many areas of science: in linguistics, philosophy, formal and mathematical logic. Each of these independent sciences defines the phenomenon of the category of negation according to the characteristics of this science. Therefore, it is necessary to recognize that the problem of denial is multifaceted. However, according to Bondarenko V.N., special attention must be paid to the logical-semantic function of negation in language since logical negation is the essence of language. As for negation in the structure of an English sentence, according to the nature of the attitude towards reality expressed in the sentence, they are divided into affirmative and negative. Denial is often accompanied by affirmation, both potential and expressed. Sentences that include grammatically formulated negation and affirmation are called negative-affirmative. Such sentences can be either simple or complex. With a non-union connection between parts of a complex sentence, the combination of affirmation/negation can be one of the means of communication that also

serves to express the meaning of comparison. Two negative particles sometimes form an affirmative sentence (a sentence with a double negative), since it involves the negation of a negation. In English, negation in a sentence can be expressed: a) in the subject: A woman become like their mothers. That is their tragedy. No man does. That's his tragedy. All women become like their mothers. This is their tragedy. No man does this. This is his tragedy. That is not very pleasant. Indeed, it is not even decent. It's not very pleasant. In fact, it's even indecent. In the last example in the English sentence, the negation is expressed using the negative particle not, and when translated into Russian, the negation is also conveyed by the negative particle not. c) in addition: I know nothing, Lady Blacknell. I don't know anything, Lady Blacknell) in the circumstances of time: I never saw a woman so altered; she looks quite twenty years younger. I have never seen a woman so changed: she looks twenty years younger. e) for the entire sentence (using a negative conjunction): There were no cucumbers in the market this morning, sir. There were no cucumbers at the market this morning, sir. It should be noted that in one sentence a combination of negation in the main part of the sentence and negation in the verb phrase is possible. In infinitive, gerundial and participial constructions, negation can be expressed: a) with the leading component - a non-predicative form: His father, not liking the idea of his going on the stage, had insisted on this. His father, who didn't like the idea of him going on stage, insisted on it. b) with any subordinate component: Long after the lorry had gone... Lanny stood there, staring at nothing, thinking of nothing, feeling nothing. In infinitive, gerundial and participial constructions, as in the whole sentence, in English, unlike Russian, there can be only one negation: Not having any friends \ having no friends. "Not having any friends." However, it is quite possible to have two negatives: in the main part of the sentence and in a construction with a non-predicative form, for example: Would it not be better not to tell your father? Speaking about ways to express negation in English, it should be noted that there are different approaches to classifying data. For example, linguists such as L.S. Barkhudarov and Stehling D.A. There are three ways of expression: - negative pronouns: Nobody wanted to talk about it after that. After that, no one wanted to talk about it. - adverbs: Never thought that he was a spy. - negative conjunctions: neither... nor, not... nor, but neither of you knew him as I did. But none of you knew him like I did. Bondarenko V.N. in his monograph "Negation as a Logicogrammatical Category" he identifies the following six ways of expression: negative affixes; negative particles; negative pronouns and adverbs; negative conjunctions; negative prepositions are postpositions in some languages; as well as an implicit way of expressing negation. Next, we should consider the most common means of expressing negation in English in their linguistic categories. Morphological ways of expressing negation include affixation, represented by prefixation and suffixation. In the word formation processes occurring in the English language, they occupy a special position. The most extensive group of prefixes in the English language are negative prefixes. The prefix un- is a very productive prefix and easily forms new words from different parts of speech. Most often this prefix is found in adjectives and adverbs, for example: The only thing that makes me unhappy is that I'm making you unhappy. The only thing that makes me unhappy is that I make you unhappy. Just as with the negative particle not, words with the prefix unexpress not just negation, but a new quality, a new attribute. Usually, antonyms from adjectives with un- are formed using the suffix less-, for example: careful - careless (uncareful) The barometer is useless: it is as misleading as the newspaper forecast. The barometer is useless: it is as misleading as the forecast in the newspaper. The prefix in- of Latin origin,

related to the Germanic prefix un-, appeared in borrowed words from French: incorrect indifferent The prefix in- has variants il-, im-, ir-; il- in words starting with l-, im- in words starting with p-, b-, m-, and ir- in words starting with r-, for example: illegal illiterate The prefix mis- is of common Germanic origin. It most often forms derivatives from verbal stems, for example: mistrust miscredit Some words have words of negativity, while others have "incorrectness" in the expression of action: miscalculate - to make a mistake in calculation ("incorrectness") mistrust - not to trust ("negativity"). The prefix dis- is of Latin origin, appeared in English in the Middle English period as part of borrowed French words: disarm discover Like most word-forming elements of non-original English origin, the prefix dis- as a means of forming English words began to be used both with stems of French origin and with English one's basics. This prefix forms derivatives from the stems of nouns, verbs, adjectives: I do not want the reader to think I am making a mystery of whatever it was that happened to Larry during the war that so profoundly affected him, a mystery that I shall disclose at a convenient moment. I do not want the reader to think that I am making a secret of anything that happened to Larry during the war that shook him so deeply, a secret that I will reveal at the appropriate moment. The meaning of this prefix, or rather the meaning obtained by a derivative word with this prefix, is the negation of the quality, attribute or action expressed by the base of the derivative word. The prefix anti- is of Greek origin; it is larger than the listed prefixes and retains its lexical meaning - 'against'. Most often it is found in words expressing socio-political and scientific concepts: antifascist, anticyclone, anticlimax, antithesis. The prefix counter- is of Latin origin, as well as anti, retains its lexical meaning, which is why some researchers call it prepositional. Most common in socio-political literature, its independence is supported by writing with a hyphen: counter-act, counterbalance, counter-poise, counter-move. So, we can draw the following conclusions: in the presence of negative suffixes and prefixes, a significant majority of negative affixes are prefixes. Many researchers note that the compatibility of negative affixes with the stems of various parts of speech varies both from language to language and within the same language. For adjectives and (less often) nouns, the prefixes most often used are un- (a homonym to the verb un-), non-, in- (im-, il-, ir-, dis-, mis-. The closest in meaning are the prefixes un-, pop-, in-, as evidenced by the existence of doublet words that differ little from each other in their meanings: nonprofessional - unprofessional, unacceptable - unacceptable. Thus, negative affixes in English are attached only to nominal stems. Verb stems are not combined with negative affixes, because verbal negation is conveyed in this language by the analytical form of the verb with the particle not. Now let us dwell on the lexical means that convey negative meanings: these are negative verbs, nouns, adverbs, pronouns. The actual lexical way of expressing negation is the way of expressing when using verbs with a negative meaning, such verbs include: -to deny (not to do, not to decide) -to doubt (to doubt) - to fail (to fail, not to cope) This method of negation also applies to some nouns: - failure (failure, collapse) -lack (lack, lack) And also to negative adverbs: hardly (hardly) scarcely (barely) This way of expressing negation by parts of speech is the actual lexical way of expressing negation. The very words used in speech carry negative semantics. This is a fairly common method. Negation can move freely from one part of speech to another. Negative pronouns indicate the absence of an object or attribute. They are correlative, on the one hand, with indefinite pronouns, on the other hand, with generalizing ones, denying the existence of the concept that the mentioned pronouns express. The pronoun no is combined with all classes of nouns with which the affirmative indefinite pronoun some

and the interrogative indefinite pronoun any appear. With objective nouns, no serves as a definition and is used only in the determining function: No cab came buy, but the street boys did... The negative pronoun no expresses the absence of something and is used as an adjective pronoun: That's no reason why I should have it. Complex negative pronouns are used as the objective member of a sentence. The genitive form of the pronoun nobody (no one), acting as a determiner, can simultaneously serve as a determiner of a noun, for example: It's nobody's fault, but your own. Compound negative pronouns delimit person from 'non-person'. Nobody, no one – personal, nothing – objective. Both structures are similar to complex indefinite and generalizing pronouns: He cared for nobody and for nothing – except dominion and the wonders of his brain. The pronoun none can be personal and objective, have a singular or plural meaning; it appears in the sentence as an objective member: None, not even Mary, dared cross-examine Ralph... The service function none is to replace the phrase 'definition + definable': There was no apparent slope downward, and distinctly none upward, so for as a casual observer might have seen. (none = no slope) Since the pronoun none is the equivalent of a substantivized phrase, it is combined with a verb in both singular and plural form, depending on the meaning of the phrase: None of them is going to get anything of me. None can replace combinations with nouns denoting both people and objects (personal and impersonal): - "Have you got any spare pencil?" - "Nor, I have none..." The group of negative pronouns includes the pronoun neither, which indicates that neither of the two mentioned persons performs the action and is not the subject of the state. In a sentence, the pronoun neither is used as an objective member of a sentence or definition: Neither spoke, but the conversation that one could imagine was clearly as follows. In the definition function, neither serves as a definition of an objective noun: neither book, nor friend. Now let's look at the expression of negation using the particle not. Particles in English are function words that are used to strengthen, clarify, limit or deny other words or phrases in a sentence. These are unchangeable words that clarify the meaning of other words, giving modal or expressive shades to other words or groups of words. They serve to form a semantic connection or grammatical form of a word and belong to the auxiliary parts of speech. The particle not most often refers to the predicate and through it to the entire content of the entire sentence, for example: This did not prevent Julia from falling madly in love with him. This didn't stop Julia from falling madly in love with him. The particle is not the main means of forming a negative sentence, but it can give a negative meaning to a word in cases where it appears with a singular noun with an indefinite article and emphasizes the complete absence of the object denoted by the noun, for example: Not a head turned to see us. Not a single head turned in our direction = No one turned their head in our direction. The negative particle is not found in the following syntactic constructions, depending on the speaker's goals to create a negative connotation of one or another part of the construction: Giving a negative meaning to a predicate verb: "Six weeks isn't really long" she said... Giving part of a sentence a negative character: Not one little sound of beast or bird or tree; not one bee humming! The answer to a question combined with an adverb or modal is: "Then there's no danger?" - "Certainly not!" To negate a statement (with a negative pronoun): "Are you going to tell him all about it?" - "Not I". "Will he come and tell us?" - "Not he." "I take a degree!" - cried - "Not I" To negate a predicate (after words expressing opinion, such as: to hope, to think, to believe, etc.): "A man or your caliber is not likely to be ignorant of it" - "I hope not." After the conjunctions or, whether (if)...or, the particle does not adjoin the verbs: When I opened the door, ...believe me

or not, madam, ...that man was gone! The pronoun none can be personal and objective, have a singular or plural meaning; it appears in the sentence as an objective member: None, not even Mary, dared cross-examine Ralph... The service function none is to replace the phrase 'definition + definable': There was no apparent slope downward, and distinctly none upward, so for as a casual observer might have seen. (none = no slope) Since the pronoun none is the equivalent of a substantivized phrase, it is combined with a verb in both singular and plural form, depending on the meaning of the phrase: None of them is going to get anything of me. None can replace combinations with nouns denoting both people and objects (personal and impersonal): - "Have you got any spare pencil?" - "Nor, I have none..." The group of negative pronouns includes the pronoun neither, which indicates that neither of the two mentioned persons performs the action and is not the subject of the state. In a sentence, the pronoun neither is used as an objective member of a sentence or definition: Neither spoke, but the conversation that one could imagine was clearly as follows. In the definition function, neither serves as a definition of an objective noun: neither book, nor friend. Now let's look at the expression of negation using the particle not. Particles in English are function words that are used to strengthen, clarify, limit or deny other words or phrases in a sentence. These are unchangeable words that clarify the meaning of other words, giving modal or expressive shades to other words or groups of words. They serve to form a semantic connection or grammatical form of a word and belong to the auxiliary parts of speech. The particle not most often refers to the predicate and through it to the entire content of the entire sentence, for example: This did not prevent Julia from falling madly in love with him. This didn't stop Julia from falling madly in love with him. The particle is not the main means of forming a negative sentence, but it can give a negative meaning to a word in cases where it appears with a singular noun with an indefinite article and emphasizes the complete absence of the object denoted by the noun, for example: Not a head turned to see us. Not a single head turned in our direction = No one turned their head in our direction. The negative particle is not found in the following syntactic constructions, depending on the speaker's goals to create a negative connotation of one or another part of the construction: Giving a negative meaning to a predicate verb: "Six weeks isn't really long" she said... Giving part of a sentence a negative character: Not one little sound of beast or bird or tree; not one bee humming! The answer to a question combined with an adverb or modal is: "Then there's no danger?" - "Certainly not!" To negate a statement (with a negative pronoun): "Are you going to tell him all about it?" - "Not I". "Will he come and tell us?" - "Not he." "I take a degree!" - cried - "Not I" To negate a predicate (after words expressing opinion, such as: to hope, to think, to believe, etc.): "A man or your caliber is not likely to be ignorant of it" - "I hope not." After the conjunctions or, whether (if)...or, the particle does not adjoin the verbs: When I opened the door, ...believe me or not, madam, ...that man was gone! Thus, lexical means of expressing negation are those means in whose very semantics there is negation. In this case, the negative characteristic of a word from one part of speech freely passes into another part of speech in the process of word formation. Along with other means, lexical means provide the speaker with a rich choice of shades of negation, allow him to operate with linguistic means as accurately as possible, form a particular linguistic situation, and achieve his goals in his speech. The syntactic way of expressing negation is possible because the dialectically interconnected grammatical categories of affirmation and negation constitute a binary one-dimensional, therefore neutralizable, opposition. The common semantic feature of the members of this opposition is

the establishment of a semantic connection in a sentence between concepts expressing an actor or action, an object and a sign of an object. The differential feature of this opposition is the nature of this semantic connection: if the connection between the concepts of agent and action is qualified as positive, the sentence implements a grammatical statement (you won my bet): if the semantic connection between them is regarded as absent, the negative sentence is actualized (you did not win my bet). It is generally accepted that the main content of linguistic negation is formal-logical negative meanings - the meaning of non-inherence, non-belonging to an object of any attribute, non-existence, non-existence, absence of an object.

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